

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF VICHARCHIKA (ECZEMA) - A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Eczema, an inflammatory skin disorder characterized by itching, redness, and exudation, closely correlates with *Vicharchika* described in Ayurveda. A 53-year-old female presented with diffuse scaly lesions, severe itching, burning, and discharge for eight months. Based on classical features, the case was diagnosed as *Vicharchika*. The patient was treated with *Rakta Shodhaka* and *Kushtahara Shamana Aushadhis* along with *Virechana*, *Raktamokshana*, *Dhavana* and *Dhoopan*. Complete remission was achieved within five months, and no relapse was observed even after one year of follow-up, indicating *Apunarbhavatva* (non-recurrence). This case demonstrates the effectiveness and long-term benefits of Ayurvedic management in *Vicharchika* (Eczema).

KEYWORDS: Vicharchika, Eczema, Raktamokshan, Dhavana, Dhoopan, Apunarbhava, Case study.**INTRODUCTION**

Eczema and dermatitis are often used synonymously to describe inflammatory skin disorders with variable clinical and histopathological features. Based on histologic patterns, dermatitis is classified into acute, sub-acute, and chronic stages. Acute dermatitis presents with vesiculation and mononuclear cell infiltration, whereas chronic dermatitis shows epidermal acanthosis, hyperkeratosis, dermal fibrosis, and perivascular inflammatory changes. Globally, dermatitis affects approximately 245 million people (around 3.3% of the population), and eczema constitutes a major portion of dermatological cases encountered in general practice.

In Ayurveda, *Vicharchika* is one among the *Kshudra Kushta* (minor skin disorders) that closely resembles eczema in its clinical presentation. It is characterized by *Kandu* (itching), *Pidika* (papules), *Shyava Varna* (dark discoloration), and *Bahusrava* (excessive discharge). The line of treatment for *Vicharchika* is not mentioned separately in classical texts; hence, management is planned according to the predominance of *Dosha* and the strength of the *Roga* (disease) and *Rogi* (patient).

This case report presents the successful management of a chronic case of *Vicharchika* (Eczema) through Ayurvedic interventions, resulting in complete remission within five months and sustained *Apunarbhavatva* (non-recurrence) over a one-year follow-up period.

Patient Information

A 53 year old female patient visited Panchakarma Outpatient department of SSAM Hospital, 13/1/24 with complaints of diffuse scaly skin lesions over upper limbs, lower limbs associated with severe itching, watery discharge, burning sensation, pain and swelling since 8 months. Clinical sign and symptoms like *Kandu* (Itching sensation), *Pidika* (Papule) *Lalima* (Redness), *Burning Sensation* (Daah), *Shoth* (Swelling), *Shool* (Pain) and *Srava* (Exudation) were present. She had taken treatment from general physician and Specialized Doctors but found no relief, then she came here for further management.

Associated Complaints

She had disturbed sleep due to itching and burning sensation.

Habits: taking curd, milk (Twice a day), Spicy, oily food,

Tea (3 times/day), Mishry (Tobacco)

other treatment, disturbed sleep, burning sensation and itching.

Past History

No h/o Diabetes mellitus/Hypertension, other major medical and surgical history.

Clinical Findings: Vital signs were normal. The sleep of the patient was disturbed due to itching. On Integumentary system examination, distribution of the skin lesion was over the upper and lower limbs. Type of lesion was papules, vesicles and scaly lesions. The colour was Redish-black associated with rough surface and serous discharge.

Family History

No relevant family history.

Psychological Evaluation

Patient was in stress due to no relief despite taking every

Timeline

Table 1: Timeline.

Date	Relevant medical history
May 2023	Acute onset of skin lesion over legs associated with itching Gradual development of skin lesions over other body parts
June 2023	Severe itching and burning sensation started
July 2023	Disturbed sleep due to itching Started allopathic treatment (Corticosteroids and ointment)
September 2023	Symptoms reappeared Took Specialized allopathic treatment (Again Corticosteroids and ointments)
January 2024	Consulted in outpatient department of SSAM hospital

Diagnostic Assessment

Strotas Pareeksha: Raktavaha Srotas.

Symptoms - Daha (Burning sensation), Kandu (Itching),

Pain (Shool), Lalima (Redness), Shoth (Swelling), Strav (Watery Discharge), Kotha (Skin eruptions).^[4]

Diagnosis - Sravi Vicharchika (Eczema contact)

Table 2: Intervention with Outcome.

Date	Oral Medication with dose and Procedure	Outcomes
13/1/2024	1. Tab. Raktapachak – 1BD (after meal) 2. Tab. Gokshuradi Guggul – 1BD (after meal) 3. Tab. Citazil – 1BD (after meal) 4. Tab. Divderma – 2BD (after meal) 5. Cap. Grab – 1 TDS (after meal) 6. Septiloc Lotion – for local application 7. Yog – Avipattikar (60gm) + manjishtha (60gm) + daruharidra (60gm) + khadir (60gm) + pippali (15 gm) + tankan (15gm) + gairik (15gm) + ananta (60gm) + vidang (60gm) + musta (60gm) = ½ table spoon (15gm) BD, after meal. (30 days yog) 8. Dhawan with Triphala and Manjishtha Kwath 9. Dhoopan with Dhoopan Varti Made up of Haridra + Vaikhanda + Hing + guggul paste in til tel	Consultation was done
27/1/2024	1 to 9 10. Virechan with Mahatiktak Ghrit and Abhayadi Modak	Itching, Swelling and discharge started to reduce
24/2/2024	1 to 9 11. Raktamokshan	Itching and Swelling reduced. No discharge.
23/3/2024	1 to 9	Itching reduced with no swelling seen.
27/4/2024	1 to 7	Almost asymptomatic Mild Itching and dark pigmentation seen
25/5/2024	1 to 7	Major relief, small patches of dark pigmentation.
24/6/2024	1 to 7	Completely asymptomatic with healthy normal skin.

Fig - A

Fig - B

Fig - C

Fig - D

Fig - E

Fig - F

Fig -G

Fig -H

Fig -I

Fig -J

Fig - A,B,C,D,E,F, are the photographs before intervention.

Fig - G,H,I,J are the photographs after intervention.

DISCUSSION

The diagnosis of *Vicharchika* (Eczema) was made based on characteristic symptoms such as *Kandu* (itching), *Pidika* (papules), *Shyava Varna* (blackish discoloration),

and *Bahusrava* (oozing). According to Ayurveda, *Vicharchika* is a *Rakta Pradoshaja Vyadhi* with predominant vitiation of *Kapha* and *Pitta Dosha*. Hence, the line of management was planned with the objectives

of *Rakta Shodhana* (blood purification), *Dosha Shamana* (pacification of vitiated doshas), and *Srotoshodhana* (cleansing of microchannels).

The patient was treated through a combination of *Shodhana* and *Shamana* therapies. *Virechana* (instant purgation) and *Raktamokshana* (bloodletting) were performed for systemic detoxification and *Pitta-Kapha Shodhana*. *Dhavana* (herbal wash) with *Triphala* and *Manjishtha Kwatha* was used externally to cleanse the lesions and reduce local inflammation. *Dhoopana* with *Haridra*, *Vaikhand*, *Hing*, and *Guggulu* in *Tila Taila* base provided antiseptic, *Kandughna* (anti-itching), and *Vranashodhana* (wound-purifying) effects.

The *Shamana Aushadhis* were carefully selected to address *Rakta Dushti* and *Pitta-Kapha Prakopa*.

- **Tab. Raktapachak** acted as a *Rakta Shodhaka* and *Pitta Shamaka*, aiding in purification of blood and reduction of inflammation.
- **Tab. Gokshuradi Guggulu** served as a *Mutrala* and *Shothahara*, supporting detoxification through urinary channels.
- **Tab. Citazil, Cap. Grab** and **Tab. Divderma** provided *Kushtaghna* and *Kandughna* effects, promoting skin healing and relief from itching.
- **Topical application of Septiloc Lotion** maintained local hygiene and prevented secondary infection.
- The **Yogic formulation** comprising *Avipattikar Churna*, *Manjishtha*, *Daruharidra*, *Khadira*, *Pippali*, *Tankan*, *Gairika*, *Ananta*, *Vidanga*, and *Musta* was given for one month. This combination is *Tikta-Kashaya Rasa Pradhana*, *Rakta Shodhaka*,

Kushtaghna, *Kandughna*, and *Deepana-Pachana*, which collectively improve metabolism and purify blood.

This multi-dimensional approach effectively broke the *Samprapti* (pathogenesis) of *Vicharchika* by addressing both systemic and local factors. Significant improvement was observed within 15 days in terms of itching, discharge, and erythema. Complete remission was achieved within five months of treatment, and the patient remained symptom-free after one year of follow-up, demonstrating *Apunarbhavatva* (non-recurrence). This highlights the efficacy of Ayurvedic management in achieving both curative and preventive outcomes in chronic skin disorders like *Vicharchika* (*Eczema*)

CONCLUSION

Vicharchika (*Eczema*) is a chronic and relapsing skin disorder. In the present case, the combined Ayurvedic approach involving *Virechana* (purgation therapy), *Raktamokshan* (bloodletting), *Dhavana*, *Dhoopan* and *Shamana Aushadhis* (internal medications) showed remarkable efficacy in reducing the symptoms of eczema. The observed improvements suggest that such integrative Ayurvedic therapies can play a significant role in managing recurrent dermatological conditions and encourage further clinical research in this field.

Patient Perspective: The patient reported high satisfaction with the treatment, noting significant relief in itching, burning sensation, discharge, and improved sleep quality.

Patient Consent: Written informed consent for the publication of this case report was obtained from the patient.

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